

PROTOTYPE DEVELOPMENT AND DESIGN/ANALYSIS OF A COMPOSITE CAB OF A LIGHT OFF-ROAD VEHICLE

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SUMMARY: The paper presents the main aspects concerning the prototype development of a composite cab of a light off-road vehicle intended to serve a vary wide variety of functions. The selection of composite structure mechanical properties is the most important activity in the development of composite material body. For that purpose several different composite structures used for composite material body production have been examined. The obtained results from mechanical tests were compared with the identical composite structures presented in the literature. The light off-road vehicle is modeled using Integrated CAD/CAM/CAE system for developing structures with composite materials. Some results of large static and dynamical investigation are presented.

KEYWORDS: Composite Cab, Composite Material Body, Light Off-Road Vehicle, Composite Structures, Modeling of Light Off-Road Vehicle, Structural Analysis.

INTRODUCTION

Application of composite materials in production of vehicle bodies is the largest substitution of sheet metal in automobile industry. The idea to produce composite material body in only one part comes as a result of mechanical properties of composites. Sheet metal bodies are manufactured of many parts produced by expensive tools/dies and processes justified only in mass production. The cost of molds for manufacturing composite material bodies is much less, but production technology is limited, slow and with a great involvement of manual work, which justify the use of composite material technology in small and medium size production. Integrated CAD/CAM/CAE system for vehicle with composite material body has been developed [3,1,2,] for modeling, analysis and production of structures with composite materials. The concept has been implemented using commercially available software (AutoCAD, 3D Studio, ALGOR) for personal computers, integrated with standard data exchange formats (DXF) and originally developed interfaces [3].

As a result of this concept we have drastically shortened the overall development process and improved quality of design, production and presentation of the product with relatively small investments in hardware and software.

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

Conceptual design is creative phase defining the basic structure of new design. It is well known that any design concept fulfills some basic requirements. Those requirements in the vehicle design are:

- minimal weight of the body
- simple and economical production technology
- simple assembly
- satisfactory level of antirust protection
- simple maintenance and service
- simple repair after small damages.

Several different variants of the vehicle were developed based on the market investigation and competitive products. Existing standards and recommendations were also included as a important criteria for development of the new vehicle. Three basic variants of composite material body structure were analyzed [3]:

A: Space frame covered with composite material plates

B: Composite material body divided in several substructures

C: Composite material body divided in two segments.

The space frame covered with composite material plates was not accepted due to the difficulties for development of different modifications of the vehicle.

The second variant, composite material body divided in several substructures, creates dilemma in comparison with the third solution. Consider very small series of light off-road vehicle production this variant can not justify investment in the production equipment.

The third variant, manufacturing of composite material body divided in two segments, with horizontal separation line of the body was accepted as the most appropriate solution. [9,10,11].

For accepted variant of light off-road vehicle, using AutoCAD modeling and drafting software, appropriate 3D models of composite material body and metal chassis have been developed (Fig. 1. and Fig. 2.).

Fig. 1: Basic geometry model of composite material body and metal chassis

Fig. 2: Basic geometry model of metal chassis

SELECTING OF COMPOSITE MATERIAL STRUCTURE

Composite materials have many characteristics that differ from those of more conventional engineering materials. They are often inhomogeneous (or heterogeneous) and nonisotropic (orthotropic or generally, anisotropic) [4,5,6]. Because of the inherent heterogeneous nature of composite materials, they are studied from two points of view, microstructural and macrostructural. At the microstructural level, composites are two phase materials, composed of reinforcement and binder. On the macrostructural level composite materials are designed with oriented layers of reinforcement-fibers bonded in the binder-matrix. Knowing of mechanical characteristics of composite materials at the macrostructural level is prerequisite for successful design of the products. Mechanical properties of composite materials depend on volume contents of reinforcement and its orientation in the composite structure [6,5,4].

To obtain appropriate composite structure for manufacturing composite material body, we have performed wide investigations of several different structures [3]. For matrix-binder a polyester resin have been used. Glass chopped mat (225 and 450 gr/m²) and woven glass fabric (580 gr/m²) and coremat (5 mm) have been used for reinforcement-fiber.

With the use of contact molding hand lay-up technique 10 different composite structures were produced [3,6]. Table 1 shows the contents of the layers in the composite structures.

Mechanical testing was performed according to ASTM D638-M standard [8,6].

Obtained testing results for composite structures with longitudinal and transversal orientation of reinforcement have shown that structures produced of layers of glass chopped mat, woven fabric and coremat behave as isotropic material. The comparison of our results (Fig. 3.) with the results of similar testing composite structures [world known literature 3,4,5,6], shows high level of closeness.

Composite material body of our light off-road vehicle is manufactured of composite structures with the best mechanical properties (F, B, D, Fig. 2. and Table 1.) [3].

Table 1: Contents of the layers in the composite structures

structure	layers gr/m ²				
	1	2	3	4	5
A	225	225	225	450	450
B	225	450	450	450	/
C	225	225	450	450	580
D	225	225	225	580	580
E	225	580	coremat	580	225
F	450	580	coremat	580	450
G	450	450	coremat	450	450
H	225	225	coremat	225	225
I	7 x 450				
J	7 x 225				

a. longitudinal orientation of reinforcement

b. transversal orientation of reinforcement

Fig. 3. Mechanical properties of investigated composite structures (according to Table 1.)

FEM MODELING OF LIGHT OFF-ROAD VEHICLE

The basic elements of the light off-road vehicle are metal chassis and composite material body. They are connected with the appropriate joint elements which provide independent behavior of both structures. Connected together, metal chassis and composite material body assure high stiffness of light off-road vehicle. In order to obtain precise values of stress and strain state, FEM models of metal chassis, composite material body and suspension were developed [3,2,1].

The presented composite material body is manufactured of several composite structures of different thickness, reinforced with ribs and close profiles. FEM model of composite material body consists of four substructures:

- floor, discretized with 1669 finite elements of sandwich thick plate type (10 mm thickness) composite structure and 1695 nodes,
- front, left, right and rear side, discretized with 1246 finite elements of thin shell type (4mm thickness) composite structure and 1482 nodes,
- roof, discretized with 704 finite elements of sandwich thick plate type (10 mm thickness) composite structure and 759 nodes,
- beam reinforcements, discretized with 1642 finite elements of beam space type and 1507 nodes.

Assembled FEM model of composite material body consists of 4172 nodes and 5261 finite elements (3619 plate/shall and 1642 beam).

The FEM model of metal chassis is discretized with 572 finite element of beam space type and 526 nodes and also with joint elements of hard rubber, placed in the connection gap between chassis and body.

The FEM model of suspension and some parts of steering mechanism is discretized combining finite element of bar space and beam space type. At joint connections some degree of freedom were removed based on the real working condition of the mechanism.

Assembled FEM models of composite material body, metal chassis and suspension is shown on Figure 4.

Fig. 4: FEM Model of Light Off-Road Vehicle

STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS

The structural analysis of the investigated light off-road vehicle with composite material body has included several different cases of static and dynamical loading of the vehicle [3]. During loads modeling, the arrangement of the useful loads and loads caused by vehicle equipment have been chosen very carefully [7,5]. The influence of location of the useful loads on the safety of the composite material body has been also studied.

The boundary conditions were defined in the way which gives only two degree of freedom to the supporting elements representing tires [7].

In the cases of symmetrical loads (torsion and braking) all supporting elements are active only in vertical direction. In case of braking we have additional load on front axle in the direction of X - axis. In this case, additionally to the adhesion force we have introduced force which simulates small shock of the front tires in the barrier [7,3,5].

The case of torsion of the vehicle simulates crossing barrier in which case two diagonal tires are elevated for 300 mm [7,3].

The case of driving of the vehicle with 140 km/h also has been studied as a load caused by the wind (Fig. 5.).

Fig. 5: Statical FEM model of Light Off-Road Vehicle

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

FEM analysis have been performed using commercial package ALGOR-FEA, module for composite structure analysis. From the results obtained it is possible to identify statical and dynamical behavior of composite body structure under various boundary conditions and loading.

The analysis of stress and strain of the investigated vehicle, and particularly the case of intensive breaking, have shown the maximal stress value in front of the composite body and metal chassis. In all analyzed cases increased stress value have appeared in the joint elements of composite body and metal chassis.

In case of torsion of the structure, substantial displacements have been identified, mainly caused by the type of selected vertical springs and elasticity of the metal chassis.

Figures 6 and 7 show maximal principal stresses in case of load caused by the wind and displacements in case of torsion.

Theoretical analysis and experimental verification of analytical results have shown that the design of light off-road vehicle with composite material body satisfy the criteria of stability and safety.

Fig. 6: Maximal principal stress in statical case applied on wind resistance

Fig. 7: Maximal displacement in statical case - torsion

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